

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF PARACETAMOL DRUG BY USE ETHYL 2-(4-NITROPHENYL) ACETATE (M9) LAP REAGENT PREPARED

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Abstract: Sensitive, fast, accuracy spectrophotometric method developed to determination of paracetamol drug depend on reaction between drug and sodium nitrite solution in acid medium to produced dizonium salt and react with M9 reagent in basic solution, the final product of the reaction was formed, which was immediately yellow stable for more than 60 minutes, which is a sufficient time to measure many samples. The highest absorption was given at 429 nm, where it follows Beer's law in the range of concentrations between 5 - 40 µg/ml. The molar absorption coefficient 3177.05 litres. mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹ and Sandel sensitivity 0.0476 µg. cm⁻², r= 0.9988, LOD was 0.1413 µg/ml, and LOQ was 0.4281 µg/ml. and the method was successfully applied to paracetamol in pharmaceutical preparations.

Keywords: azo dye, determination, hydrazine, paracetamol, spectrophotometric.

Introduction

Paracetamol called acetaminophen, it is a common form of pain relief and temperature reduction [1]. Its chemical name is N-acetyl-p-aminophenol, and its chemical formula is C₈H₉NO₂. The first innovation of paracetamol, which was launched by the American chemist Harmon Northrop Morse [2] in 1878, was a mixture of acetylacetone and ammonia. It is also known by several brand names, such as Panadol, Tylenol (derived from N-acetyl-para-amino phenol), and Panadol Extra. [3,4] It is commonly sold as an important ingredient in many cold and flu remedies. It is usually taken orally but is also available in intravenous form (1-4). Paracetamol is available in the form of tablets, drops, caps, injections, and syrup. [5] Paracetamol is usually safe in appropriate doses. The maximum recommended daily dose for adults is 3 or 4 grams [6,7]. High concentrations may lead to poisoning, with paracetamol poisoning potentially being malignant. The primary source of cytolytic hepatitis is N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone-imine, a harmful metabolite of paracetamol, which leads to dose-dependent hepatocyte necrosis and death in several countries. In addition, paracetamol is used to relieve severe pain, including cancer-related pain and postoperative pain, in conjunction with opioid-based pain treatments [8]. Paracetamol has a specific effect on the brain, and this effect is aimed at blocking the enzyme involved in pain transmission. It is recognized that its mechanism of action is different from other pain relievers, but although it relieves pain throughout the body [9]. It is on the World Health Organization's List of Essential Medicines and is the most effective and safest medicine needed for a healthcare system [10]. High-performance liquid chromatography is the most routinely used method for evaluating paracetamol in pharmaceuticals, yet spectrophotometric technology remains very popular in this field [11]. Several methods have been documented in the medical literature for the determination of paracetamol in various pharmaceutical preparations, HPLC [12,13]. RP-HPLC [14-18]

HPTLC, voltammetry, electrical methods and spectrophotometry [19-29]. Several different spectrophotometric methods for measuring paracetamol have been documented in the literature [30]

Scheme 1: Paracetamol structure

Experimental

Instruments

All spectrophotometric measurements were conducted using a T90 UV-Visible Spectrophotometer manufactured by PG Instrumental Ltd. (UK). A 10mm quartz cell was utilized for these measurements. For precise weight measurements, a Sartorius Balance 210S kern was used.

Reagents and Materials

Chemicals

Chemicals and solvents used in the study from Aldrich and Fluka, USA. Melting points were determined using a Stuart melting point apparatus. Infrared spectra were obtained using KBr discs and a Shimadzu FTIR-8100 spectrophotometer. ThirteenC-NMR spectra were acquired using an MHZ spectrometer with DMSO-d₆ as a solvent, while 1H-NMR spectra were obtained using the same apparatus. The purity of compounds was assessed using TLC on alumina sheets percolated in silica gel (type 60 F254 Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Chemicals and solvents were used without further purification. paracetamol was provided by the State Company for Drug Industries and Medical Appliance (SDI), Samarra, Iraq. Distilled water was used in the preparation of all solutions. Panda, Paracetamol, Joswe, Jordan, Piodol, Paracetamol, Pioneer, Iraq, Panadol, Paracetamol, Glaxosmithkline, Ireland. Distilled water was employed in the preparation of all solutions.

Solutions

A 1000 µg/ml paracetamol solution was prepared by dissolving 0.25 g of paracetamol powder in distilled water and then completing the volume 250 ml volumetric vial. As for the reagent solution was prepared by dissolving 0.3825g of Laboratory prepared reagent in ethanol, then completing the volume to the mark with ethanol in a 250 ml volumetric vial. The sodium nitrite solution was prepared by dissolving 0.1725 grams of sodium nitrite powder in distilled water, then completing the volume to the mark in a 250 ml volumetric bottle with distilled water. Additionally, solutions of 1.0 M hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, and sulfuric acid were prepared by diluting the respective acids with Distilled water in 100 mL volumetric flasks.

Additionally, solutions of 1.0 M Sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide, ammonium hydroxide, prepared in 100 mL volumetric flasks.

Solutions of interfering substances

A solution (glucose, fructose, lactose, sucrose, magnesium citrate, sodium sulfate, starch, cellulose) was prepared 1000 µg/ml by dissolving 0.1000 grams of it in 5 ml of ethanol, then adding the volume to 100 ml of distilled water.

Sample Preparation

The pharmaceutical solution was prepared 1000 µg/ml by taking 10 tablets of the pharmaceutical preparation (Paracetamol, Paracetamol), (Panda, Paracetamol) (Piodol, Paracetamol) (Panadol, Paracetamol), and their weights were (6.5847, 5.5231, 6.4360 and 6.2676 grams, respectively). They were

ground well, and weights of (0.521, 0.542, 0.532, 0.551) grams were taken from them, respectively. dissolved in distilled water, filtered, washed several times, and the volume was Complete to the mark in a volumetric bottle of (500 ml) with distilled water.

Preparation of hydrazide Ethyl 2-(4-nitrophenyl)acetate[31-33]

It was made by dissolving (0.01 mol, 2.09 g) of 2-(4-nitrophenyl)acetate ethyl ester in (25 ml) of absolute ethanol, and adding (0.04 mol, 8.37 ml) of hydrazine (99%) dropwise with Stir constantly. The mixture rises for approximately (4) hours. After that, the contents of the beaker were poured into ice for an hour, then it was filtered and crystallized with ethanol to give a yellow-colored precipitate with a melting point of (165-167) degrees Celsius, and the yield was (82%).

Preparation and diagnosis of hydrazide Ethyl 2-(4-nitrophenyl)acetate

Hydrazide was prepared by combining (4) moles of hydrazine and ethyl alcohol with one mole of absolute 2-(4-nitrophenyl)acetate ethyl ester, and the reaction is as follows:

The process or mechanics was as follows: [34-37]

Results

The prepared compound was characterized laboratory-wise as it shared its physical properties, including the change in melting color and the change in the compound. In addition, a test (flow velocity rate) was performed on the results, which contributes to a single characteristic spot (TLC). In addition, it was identified On the hydrazide compound by measuring infrared spectra (IR) and magnetic resonance radiation (1H-13C-NMR), the infrared spectrum showed two bands at 3303 and (3375 cm⁻¹), belonging to the symmetrical and asymmetrical (NH₂) stretch. In addition to a band at (3012) cm⁻¹, dating back to (Ar-H) stretch, as well as a band at (3180) cm⁻¹, dating to (NH) stretch, and two bands at (1666) cm⁻¹, dating back to (NH) stretch. (C=O), and two bands at (1465 and 1556 cm⁻¹), dating back to the rheumatic (C=C) stretch, And a band at (1257) cm⁻¹ belongs to the (C-N) stretch, and two bands at (1311) and (1510 cm⁻¹) go back to the (NO₂) stretch, and a band at (1174) cm⁻¹ goes back to the (137) stretch. N-N[38-40], shows the infrared (IR) spectrum of the compound. The proton nuclear magnetic resonance (1H-NMR) spectrum of compound showed a signal at the position (3.39 ppm) belonging to the protons of (CH₂), as well as two binary signals in the ppm range (7.21-7.76) belonging to the H protons of the aromatic ring. With the appearance of a single signal at the ppm (8.55) site belonging to the (NH) proton of the amine, as well as a signal at the ppm (4.02) site belonging to the (NH₂) protons, and a signal at the ppm (2.49) site dating back to the protons of the solvent d₆ (DMSO)[41-43]. When studying the (13C-NMR) spectrum of the prepared

compound (M9), it was revealed that a signal appeared at the position (ppm 31.77), which belongs to the carbon (CH₂), and multiple signals in the ppm range (142.27-127.44), which belong to the carbons of the aromatic ring, as well as A signal at the ppm site (165.63) belongs to the carbon of the carbonyl group (C=O), in addition to the appearance of signals at the ppm range 39.37-40.62) belonging to the carbonate of the solvent (DMSO)[44,45]. (Figure1,2,3).

Figure (1) FT-IR spectrum of the detector

Figure (2) 1H-NMR spectrum of the detector

Figure (3) 13C-NMR spectrum of the detector

Effect of the amount of sodium nitrite

The effect of different volumes (0.25- 2) mL of sodium nitrite solution on the absorbance colored of Azo dye product. (Figure 4).

Figure (4): Effect of the amount of sodium nitrite

Effect of the amount of coupling reagentM9

The effect of different volumes of M9 solution on the absorbance of the colored product studied, keeping other conditions constant (Figure 5).

Figure (5): Effect of reagent quantity reagentM9

Effect of acid type

In this study, three types of acids were taken at (1 molar) for each, and they were reacted with paracetamol sample, which gave the highest absorption value. (Figure 6).

Figure (6): Effect of acid type

Effect of acid amount

The effect of different volumes of 1M HCl solution on the colored product studied it illustrated (Figure 7).

Figure (7): Effect of the amount of acid

Effect of the type of basic solution

The effect of different alkaline solution 1M for example (sodium hydroxide, ammonium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and sodium carbonate) studied, of sodium hydroxide the best obtained stability of solution color.(Figure 8).

Figure (8): Effect of the type of basic solution

Effect of the amount of basic solution

The effect of the amount of basic solution was studied, where different volumes were taken, (2 - 0.25 ml), and the absorbance was measured at (429 nm), as the best volume added was (1 ml). (Figure 9).

Figure (9): Effect of the amount of basic solution

Final absorption spectrum

The final absorption spectrum was measured after reaching the optimum conditions, which are using 0.3 ml of paracetamol 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 1 ml of hydrochloric acid 1 M, and 5 ml of the sodium nitrite. 10^{-2} M. After 8 min., (0.5 ml) of reagent 10^{-2} M and 1 ml of sodium hydroxide 1 M were added. After another 8 minutes, the volume was completed with distilled water. To the mark in a 10 ml volumetric bottle the absorbance of the yellow product was measured against its blank solution, which gave the highest absorption at 429 nm. (Figure 10).

Figure (10): Final absorption spectrum for determination paracetamol

Procedure for construction of calibration curve

A series of volumetric bottles with a capacity of (10 ml) were taken containing different concentrations (5 - 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of paracetamol, which is equivalent to volumes from 0.05-0.4 ml 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and 1 ml of Hydrochloric acid 1 M) and 5 ml of sodium nitrite 10^{-2} M After the specified period according to the method of work followed, (0.5 ml) of a reagent M9 10^{-2} M) was added and 1 ml of sodium hydroxide 1 M and after 8 minutes the volume was completed with distilled water to the mark. Then the absorbance of the solutions was measured against the blank solution at 429 nm. Figure (11) represents the calibration curve that follows Beer's law in the range of concentrations (5 - 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) for paracetamol. where a correlation coefficient of (0.9980) was given, and the molar absorbance value was $3177.05 \text{ Lmol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$. Sandel sensitivity $0.0476 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$.

Figure (11): Calibration curve for paracetamol

Accuracy and compatibility of the proposed method

The accuracy and compatibility of the proposed method were calculated using the previous equations, and from measuring three different concentrations of paracetamol at the optimal conditions indicated in the working method. The results obtained show that the method has good accuracy and compatibility. (Table 1,2).

Table (1): Accuracy and compatibility of the proposed method

D (ppm)		Rec%	RSD%
Present μ	Found \bar{x}		
15	15.24	101.57	0.266
25	25.67	102.66	0.364
30	30.45	101.50	0.083

*n=3

Table (2): Results of Detection limits

Concentration $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	b	S	LOD $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	LOQ $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
blank	0.0210	0.0009	0.1413	0.4281

Effect of additives

The effect of adding an increase in the concentrations of additives present with paracetamol in the form of tablets as a pharmaceutical preparation, and in a volumetric vial of capacity (10 ml), was studied. The results show that there is no interference of these substances in the paracetamol with the reagent, by adding three concentrations of each substance, which It confirms the possibility of successfully applying this method to pharmaceutical preparations. Table 3).

Table (3): Effect of additives

Type of Interference	Conc. of Interferences (ppm)	Present Conc. of D (ppm)	Abs.	Found Conc. of D (ppm)	Erel%	Rec%
Standard	non	20	0.497	20.59	2.94	102.94
Glucose	10	20	0.49	20.27	1.33	101.33
	20	20	0.491	20.31	1.56	101.56
	40	20	0.482	19.90	-0.52	99.48
Fructose	10	20	0.484	19.99	-0.06	99.94
	20	20	0.485	20.03	0.17	100.17
	40	20	0.481	19.85	-0.75	99.25
Socaros	10	20	0.473	19.48	-2.60	97.40
	20	20	0.477	19.67	-1.67	98.33
	40	20	0.479	19.76	-1.21	98.79
Lactose	10	20	0.484	19.99	-0.06	99.94
	20	20	0.488	20.17	0.87	100.87
	40	20	0.481	19.85	-0.75	99.25
Starch	10	20	0.48	19.80	-0.98	99.02
	20	20	0.484	19.99	-0.06	99.94
	40	20	0.497	20.59	2.94	102.94
Celelos	10	20	0.49	20.27	1.33	101.33
	20	20	0.491	20.31	1.56	101.56
	40	20	0.482	19.90	-0.52	99.48
Sodium Sulfate	10	20	0.484	19.99	-0.06	99.94
	20	20	0.481	19.85	-0.75	99.25
	40	20	0.48	19.80	-0.98	99.02
Maghesume Citrate	10	20	0.484	19.99	-0.06	99.94
	20	20	0.497	20.59	2.94	102.94
	40	20	0.49	20.27	1.33	101.33

Applications

The proposed method was applied to determined paracetamol in the pharmaceutical preparation in the form of tablets. The weight of 10 tablets (Paracetol, Paracetamol), (Panda, Paracetamol) (Piodol, Paracetamol) (Panadol, Paracetamol) was taken and their weights were (6.5847, 5.5231, 6.4360, 6.2676) grams. They were ground well, and weights of (0.521, 0.542, 0.532, 0.551) grams were taken from them, respectively. They were dissolved in distilled water, filtered, the sediment was washed several times, and the volume was brought to the mark in a volumetric bottle of (500 ml) with distilled water. Three concentrations were taken from the filtrate to estimate paracetamol in the pharmaceutical preparation. (Table 4).

Table (4): Application of the proposed method for the determination of paracetamol in pharmaceutical preparations.

Industrial application	Conc. of D (ppm)		Erel %	Rec %	Abs.
	Present	Found			
Paracetol, Paracetamol (500 mg), SDI, Iraq, Tablets	10	10.19	1.92	101.92	0.270
	20	20.47	2.35	102.35	0.486
	30	31.60	5.35	105.35	0.720
Panda, Paracetamol (500 mg), Joswe, Jordan, Tablets	10	10.00	0.02	100.02	0.266
	20	20.28	1.40	101.40	0.482
	30	31.08	3.60	103.60	0.709
Piodol, Paracetamol (500 mg), Pioneer, Iraq, Tablets	10	10.14	1.44	101.44	0.269
	20	20.42	2.11	102.11	0.485
	30	30.41	1.38	101.38	0.695
Panadol, Paracetamol (500 mg), Glaxosmithkline, Ireland, Tablets	10	10.05	0.49	100.49	0.267
	20	20.76	3.78	103.78	0.492
	30	30.60	2.02	102.02	0.699

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